

Osseous response to Hydroxyl Apatite Crystals in Anterior Maxillary Defects

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ABSTRACT:

This study evaluated efficacy of Hydroxyl Apatite crystals in bone regeneration in anterior maxillary defects. In our study forty patients underwent surgery for anterior maxillary defects. Hydroxyl Apatite (HA) granules were used on 20 patients & 20 patients were treated without graft and served as the control group. All the 40 patients were followed up for 9 months to compare the rate of bone formation by taking serial IOPA x-rays at 3, 6 and 9 months. All results were calculated using the mean value and standard deviation for each of the parameters considered and checked for statistical significance using unpaired 't' test.

Evaluation of long term response of HA in osseous defects of the anterior maxilla for 9 months was excellent with no complaints from the patients. Radiographic follow up of the bony cavity favoured faster healing in lesions with Hydroxyl Apatite graft compared to the control group with no graft.

KEY WORDS: Hydroxyl apatite, maxillary bone defects, regeneration.

INTRODUCTION:

The development of new procedures in the treatment of faciomaxillary trauma and reconstructive surgery has created new challenges. Large traumatic bone defects can be covered by soft tissues but reconstruction of the bone by itself may be difficult. The use of autogenous bone has remained the gold standard in restoring bone defects, but it is not always possible to obtain enough bone. Previous bone grafting procedures may leave poor donor sites and the amount of bone needed may fall short of requirement. In addition, harvesting bone graft needs an additional surgical requirement which implies a certain amount of morbidity^[1] To avoid these problems, allograft bone stored in bone banks can be used. Unfortunately this does not solve the problems; there is a risk of secondary infection, when allograft bone is used.^[2] Biomaterials may provide a solution to these problems. An ideal bone

substitute is to be tolerated by the host tissue without any adverse reaction; it should promote bone formation, have appropriate mechanical strength, and resorb after it has fulfilled its function. Porous calcium ceramics have proved to be biocompatible bone substitutes. The material most investigated in this group is Hydroxyl Apatite (HA). It can be manufactured from natural reef building coral skeleton by a hydrothermal exchange reaction, where the trabecular, bone initiating structure of the coral remains unchanged and the calcium carbonate (CC) skeleton is converted to calcium phosphate, the main inorganic salt of bone.^[3] The major advantage of Hydroxyl Apatite grafts are that, they are relatively safe and well tolerated, offer the potential of an unlimited supply of bone substitutes, absence of donor site infection and decreased operative time.

The surgical removal of maxillary pathology and cyst are the frequently performed oral surgical procedures. The defects caused by such surgery could result in infection and other healing problems occasionally. In the surgical defect, the space occupied by pathology was filled with beta tricalcium phosphate Hydroxyl Apatite crystals. This study was undertaken

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in anterior maxillary bone defects. The aim was to study the efficacy of the material in regeneration of bone by osteoinduction and the follow up was by clinical & radiographic methods upto 9 months. This is compared with the natural replacement with bone as it would heal in patients with no bone graft substitute.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

The present study was conducted in the Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery, Modern Dental College, Indore, after all necessary clearances from the institutional ethical committee. All patients signed an informed written consent before participating in the study.

The material used in this study is Hydroxyl Apatite (HA), a bioceramic composite material, which contains 90% Hydroxyl Apatite and 10% beta-tricalcium phosphate. 'Hydroxyl Apatite - Beta tricalcium phosphate granules' is a biomaterial offering great potential correction of maxillofacial defects. It is available as natural and synthetic hydroxyapatite. The chemical and physical parameters are identical to that of human bone. It is elastic just as natural bone, is revitalized via migration of blood vessels and promotes superficial bone formation that is osteoconductive. It is slowly resorbed and gets integrated in the bone by natural remodeling process. In this study the bioceramic composite material is used in granule form to fill the bony defect after surgical removal. These granules are in white color measuring 1-2mm in size and with porosity of 500-1200 μ m.

In our study forty patients underwent surgery for anterior maxillary defects. Hydroxyl Apatite (HA) granules were used on 20 patients & 20 patients were treated without graft and served as the control group. All the 40 patients were followed up for 9 months to compare the rate of bone formation by taking serial IOPA x-rays at 3, 6 and 9 month intervals. The surgical site was followed up at the same time intervals and the clinical response was adjudged as per the following criteria : a) Pain - VAS Scale from grading 1-5; where 1 was graded as mild pain, 3 was graded as moderate & 5 was severe pain; b) Swelling - was graded as present or absent & the no. of days it took to subside was observed daily upto 7 days; c) Infection- present or absent; d) Tenderness of tooth - present or absent; e) Presence of sinus or discharge - present or absent.

For all patients the following blood investigation were carried out: Complete hemogram i.e. Hb gm% , Total Leukocyte Count (TLC), Differential Leukocyte

Count (DLC), Clotting time (CT), Bleeding time (BT), Platelet Count (PC) and test for retrovirus and Australia antigen (HbS Ag).

Inclusion criteria: All the cases were clinically evaluated for the systemic diseases and were normal ambulatory patients with acceptable oral hygiene. With the help of pre operative intraoral periapical radiograph, the type of lesion, size and location of lesion were selected. All the lesions were radiolucent within the range of 5mm x 20mm located in anterior maxillary region. In all cases, endodontic treatment was carried out beforehand as the involved teeth were non vital.

Exclusion criteria: Following patients were excluded from the present study: a) Patients with possible compromised immune status or systemic disease which might affect normal healing process eg. diabetes mellitus; b) The patients who had any unacceptable oral habits like smoking or tobacco chewing; c) Patients platelets count <1, 50,000/cu.mm with H/O bleeding disorder; d) Patients who had allergy or hypersensitivity to local anesthetics.

Strict aseptic procedures were followed. Pre operative oral rinse with 1% Betadine was given to all the patients. All the operations were performed under local anesthesia (lignocaine 2% with 1:80,000 adrenalines). The incision was made for the trapezoidal flap design which included adjacent tooth on either side of the involved tooth. BP Handle Knife No. 3 with blade number 15 was used.

The muco-periosteal flap was reflected. In most of the cases, labial plate was not intact over the apex of the root but if bone was intact an opening was made with cross cut fissure bur. Normal saline irrigation was used as a coolant and to remove debris. The curette with its concave surface facing the bone was inserted into the crypt and the granulation tissue was cleaved/ removed from the bone. The denuded root end was now ready to be amputated and the cut was made on a 45 degree Labio lingual angle. After the root tip was beveled, the cavity was again carefully debrided. All granulation tissue was removed, the wound was cleansed thoroughly with saline. Clean bare bone was visible now on all sides and the cut surface of the tooth was smooth. To maintain clean dry field and capture any debris the periapical area was packed with gauze for 5 minutes. The HA graft mixed with fresh blood was then placed into the cavity with the help of spatula and condensed by the condenser with in the appropriate margins of the adjacent walls. A collagen sheet was placed over the graft to act as an epithelial barrier before

closing. An immediate post operative IOPA x-ray was taken to assess whether the material had been packed densely or not and then the flap was closed with 3 - 0 mersilk interrupted sutures.

The control group patients were allowed to

Figure 1(A): Flap-Reflected, Curettage & Apicoectomy: Experimental Group

Figure 1(B): Placement of HA Graft: Experimental Group

Figure 2: Curettage & Apicoectomy done with no graft: Control Group

Figure 3: Measurement of Gray Level Histogram

heal without graft placement in the lesion. Surgical procedure was the same as for graft patients [Figure. 1, 2 & 3].

All the patients were given standard post operative instructions and were prescribed antibiotics – Amoxicillin 500 mg 8 hourly and non steroidal anti inflammatory analgesics (Diclofenac & Paracetamol) for a period of 5 days post operatively.

The wound sites were clinically examined for a period of 9 months for the presence of pain, edema, infection, discharge and any signs of wound dehiscence or extrusion of material. Sutures were removed after 1 week.

IOPA radiographs of the graft and the control site were taken preoperatively, immediate postop, 1 month, 6 months and 9 month post operatively.

All the radiographs were taken using the same X-ray machine and at the same setting. All the radiographs were scanned into computer with a flat bed scanner fitted with a transparency module and stored in hard disc of a personal computer. The images were imported into soft ware based on Imaging Research INC ®. A template of the region of interest was made in the preoperative radiograph on the windows. The monochromic images were converted into 8 bit type. Density values were recorded in grey levels from 0-255. The grey level values and the area of the region of interest was determined. The same template was used on the radiographs taken at immediate postop 1 month, 6 months and 9 months post operatively by using the cursor. The average of the grey values were calculated for the radiographs of the graft site and compared with that of non graft site [Figure 4].

All radiographs were arranged at random and then interpreted by two specialist one radiologist and one Endodontist. The IOPA X-rays were taken on

Figure 4: IOPA follow up for control group upto 9 months

kodak ultra speed film using the paralleling technique and film holder. Examination of the X-ray was performed at a moderately illuminated table with the use of a magnifying viewer.

RESULTS:

All the subjects completed the study. The results were evaluated based on clinical observation, radiographic analysis and densitometric analysis by gray level histogram. All results were calculated using the mean value and standard deviation for each of the parameters considered and checked for statistical significance using unpaired ‘t’ test.

We found that the post op pain was more in patients with the graft but by the 7th post op day all were comfortable and had no complaints. Swelling was comparable in both the groups of patients and it subsided by the 7th day. No appreciable difference was noted between both the groups of patients. This was probably because HA is non allergenic and non-antigenic in nature. There was no mobility or tenderness of the teeth to percussion in all the patients. All the patients returned to normal function after 3 months. None of the patients in either group presented with post op infection or discharging sinus.

Results are depicted in the Tables and Graphs 1-3.

DISCUSSION:

The Hydroxyl Apatite is radio opaque. As the material is already in its highest oxidation state, it will not oxidize further or resorb. The Histologic sequelae associated with implantation on non porous calcium phosphate biomaterials in bone can be generally characterized as being representative of normal bone healing process on and around the implant. At the interface of either dense or porous materials bone is usually deposited directly on the surfaces without the presence of an intervening fibrous tissue capsule.^[4]

Calcium phosphate implants are inert biocompatible and evoke no inflammatory or immune response when implanted in osseous or non osseous tissues. The property of calcium phosphates has been characterized as osteoconductive^[5]. Calcium phosphate ceramic biomaterials are proven to be safe and effective for a variety of clinical applications by various investigators.^[6,7,8,9] Their findings were identical to the the response we found in our patients. The clinical healing was similar in both the control group as well as the experimental group. There was no difference in the pain or swelling amongst the two groups. None of the patients developed any signs of infection. Tissue

Table 1: Comparison of mean values of gray Level Histogram in Study and Control Group : (Unpaired ‘t’ test).

Stages	Study group (n=20)	Control group (n=20)	‘t’ value	‘p’ value	Result
Post operative	56.44 ± 13.19	48.28 ± 7.48	2.41	0.020	Significant
1 month	65.65 ± 12.22	57.90 ± 9.40	2.24	0.030	Significant
6 months	87.85 ± 15.93	78.17 ± 8.62	2.39	0.021	Significant
9 months	113.97 ± 9.96	97.43 ± 9.40	5.39	<0.0001	Highly Significant

response to calcium phosphate implant materials has proved that more favorable results are possible when Hydroxyl Apatite is deeply buried and covered with a thick layer of soft tissue. Intraoral application of calcium phosphate ceramic biomaterial in the past has been predominantly used in the augmentation of atrophic alveolar ridges and regeneration of bone in periodontal defects.^[10,11]

A wide variety of surgical models have been

used to investigate calcium phosphate implants with many of them using autografts &/or empty sockets as controls. In the present study, empty anterior maxillary defects within a limited size range (5mm to 20mm) were used.

We studied the effectiveness of calcium phosphate biomaterials in maxillary surgical defects created by the removal of periapical pathology. Our study showed that the material was biocompatible and

Graph 1: Comparison of mean values of Gray Level Histogram in Study and Control Group

Table 2 : Comparison of difference of mean value of Gray Level Histogram from Post-operative to 1 month, 6 months and 9 months in Study Group & Control Group

Stages	Study group (n=20)	Control group (n=20)	't' value	'p' value	Result
Post operative to 1 month	9.21 ± 5.48	9.62 ± 6.12	0.22	0.824	Not significant
Post operative to 6 month	31.41 ± 9.89	29.89 ± 9.58	0.49	0.626	Not significant
Post operative to 9 month	57.53 ± 14.20	49.15 ± 11.83	2.02	0.049	significant

Graph 2: Comparison of differences of mean value of Gray Level Histogram form Post-operative to 1 month, 6 months and 9 months in Study Group & Control Group

Table 3: Comparison of mean values of VAS for pain in Study and Control Group.

Stages	Study group (n=20)	Control group (n=20)	't' value	'p' value	Result
Day1	2.05	2.3	1.17	0.246	Not significant
Day2	1.75	1.85	0.45	0.651	Not significant
Day3	1.05	1.20	0.72	0.471	Not significant
Day4	0.35	0.40	0.32	0.751	Not significant
Day5	0.10	0.10	0.00	1.000	Not significant
Day6	0.0	0.0	-	-	-
Day7	0.0	0.0	-	-	-

Graph 3: Comparison of mean values of VAS for Pain in Study Group and Control Group

did not show any exaggerative tissue reaction. These findings were in accordance to the earlier studies.^[14] This was assessed by measuring the swelling at various intervals post operatively. None of the cases had any post operative infection. Exfoliation of the impacted material was not observed in any of the cases. Within a period of 2-3 weeks the mucosa over the implanted area attained normal color and texture, and healed uneventfully. These findings were similar to the observations of earlier studies.^[10,15] The clinical assessment showed that the healing of soft tissues in the graft side were similar to non graft side.

Radiographically the implant material was visible throughout the observation periods. In all the defects there was evidence of a demarcation between the tricalcium phosphates implant material, bone and the proximal tooth. There was no evidence of root resorption or ankylosis of the adjacent tooth. These findings were in accordance to an earlier study.^[16]

The density changes were assessed from the radiograph. Average grey levels observed in the graft site were significantly higher than the non graft site. These findings highlight the effectiveness of computer assisted densitometric image analysis.^[16] Post operative radiological picture showed that calcium phosphate implant material placed like a dense opaque mass which were clearly distinct from surrounding bone. The radiological observation made during the follow up period showed that radio opacity of calcium sulphate ceramic material became more uniform and the periphery of the implant got blended with the surrounding bone. This indicates that there is osseous in-growth into the implant material.

This study was undertaken to test the hypothesis that if the periapical cavity could be obliterated, the success rate would be improved by eliminating hematoma formation, keeping avascular tissue at bay, promoting bony infill of the cavity and

thus reduce the recurrence of infection. We used HA to obliterate defects because of ease of use, availability and lack of donor site morbidity. With the possibility of transmission of HIV infection occurring from bank bone, research into the use of anorganic bone has been resumed.^[17]

An organic bone has been used with success following apical surgery. Placing granular form of HA stops bone bleeding and provides support to the overlying mucoperiosteal flap and prevents it from sagging into the bony defect. The particle size and shape of the HA was easy to handle and manipulate during the surgical treatment. It had good haemostatic properties and was not readily displaced from the treatment sites.^[18,19,20]

Clinical follow up revealed no major difference between the healing of the wounds. But our radiological examination was crucial in judging that the bone formation was definitely faster in the case of the experimental group.

CONCLUSION:

The response to hydroxyl apatite (HA) crystals in bone regeneration in anterior maxillary defects was excellent with no complaints from the patients up-to 9 months, the period of present study. Radiographic follow up of the bony cavity favoured faster healing in lesions with HA graft.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

This is only a prospective study to assess long term responses of Hydroxyl Apatite crystals in osseous defects of the anterior maxilla. However, the period of 9 months may be too short for follow up of bone regeneration in these defects and to judge the efficacy of the same. A longer term may be necessary to give conclusive evidence.

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